

**CREW EMERGENCY RETURN VEHICLE:
Electrical Power System Design Study**

E. C. Darcy and T. P. Barrera
NASA-Johnson Space Center
Houston, TX

ABSTRACT

The United States is committing to build a permanently manned Space Station, Freedom, located in low earth orbit. Within the five yearly planned Space Shuttle support flights to Freedom, it is postulated that an emergency could require the immediate evacuation of a crew member or the entire crew when the Shuttle is unavailable. To cover this contingency, a Crew Emergency Return Vehicle (CERV) is proposed to perform this lifeboat function. This escape module will be permanently docked to Freedom and, on demand, will be capable of safely returning the crew to earth. This work gathers the unique requirements that the CERV, designed by NASA-Johnson Space Center, presents to its power source and selects a baseline system.

Introduction

The purpose of this study is to establish the power requirements of the CERV and to evaluate various electrical power sources. The design by NASA-Johnson resembles an Apollo capsule with a larger diameter and with a more offset center of gravity (Fig. 1). The vehicle is designed for a crew of one to six. With great autonomy, it will be activated by the crew, separate from Freedom (Fig. 2), target a landing site, use a propulsion module to perform a de-orbit burn (Fig. 3), and splash down with parachutes (Fig. 4). The electrical power source of the CERV will supply power for avionics, displays and controls (D&C), environmental control and life support systems (ECLSS), communication and tracking systems (C&T), and propulsion systems for a complete mission timeline. The basic requirements are for a 29 volt system that is one failure tolerant with a minimum 4 year quiescent storage life and a maximum activation time of 10 minutes [1].

The design goals are to maximize simplicity, reliability, safety, and passivity and to minimize cost. The CERV should be simple, reliable, and available and not become a burden with its own infrastructure (ground control, return procedures, and recovery forces).

Power/Energy Requirements

Nine design reference missions (DRM) have been established. The first three involve a simple return of crew. The fourth DRM adds a capability to rescue a disabled astronaut on an extravehicular activity (EVA) while retaining DRM-1 capability. DRM-5 and 6 add unmanned and manned ascent phases, respectively, to DRM-1. The seventh DRM replaces the crew with cargo. DRM-8 involves rescuing up to five astronauts from a stranded shuttle and returning them to earth. And finally, DRM-9 provides for a temporary (24 hr) evacuation of the station (i.e., during an environmental purge). The extra capability of DRM-8 and 9 must be followed with DRM-2 capability due to the unplanned nature of those missions.

The power levels from each subsystem are listed in Table I by the four main phases of a typical mission. The first phase is an on-orbit phase for targeting a landing site. A loiter phase is included as a contingency to allow for weather to clear up at a favorable landing site. This is especially important for the ill or injured crewmen scenario, DRM-3, where the goal is to land near medical facilities. The third phase a short entry phase which includes the de-orbit burn. And finally, a recovery phase provides minimum life support for the crew while waiting for rescue forces to arrive. Table II lists a breakdown of the mission timelines. Table III ranks the missions by energy requirement.

Table I. CERV Power Requirements

	On-Orbit (W)	Loiter (W)	Entry (W)	Recovery (W)
Avionics [2]	1208	738	1208	--
D&C [3]	777	466	777	33
ECLSS [4]	1127	1127	1127	20
C&T [5]	461	369	384	30
Prop. [6]	10	10	100	--
Total Power	3583	2710	3596	83

Table II. Mission Timelines [1,7]

DRM	Orbit (hr)	Loiter (hr)	Orbit (hr)	Loiter (hr)	Entry (hr)	Recovery (hr)
1	--	--	2	7	1	24
2	--	--	2	32	1	24
3	--	--	2	12.5	1	1
4	2	--	2	7	1	24
5	7	24	2	7	1	24
6	8	23	2	7	1	24
7	--	--	2	7	1	24
8	11	--	2	32	1	24
9	2	22	2	32	1	24

Table III. CERV Energy Requirements

DRM - Mission	Time (hr)	Energy (Wh)
1 - Planned Return	34	31,724
7 - Cargo Return	34	31,724
4 - EVA Rescue	36	39,524
3 - Ambulance Return	16.5	44,720
2 - Unplanned Return	59	99,474
5 - Unmanned Ascent	66	105,313
6 - Manned Ascent	66	124,846
8 - NSTS Rescue	71	141,483
9 - Station Evacuation	83	170,384

Power Source Options

In compliance with the CERV design goals, DRM-2 was decided to be the pacing mission for power systems. However, the selected candidates also had to be capable of being optimized (scaled down) to meet DRM-1. The more ambitious missions (DRM-4,5,6,8,9) were omitted from further study.

The total power and energy requirements are then 3.6 kW and 100 kWh, respectively. The candidate sources evaluated were primary active and reserve lithium batteries, a solid polymer electrolyte (SPE) fuel cell and a primary-secondary battery with photovoltaic hybrid system.

Lithium/thionyl chloride (Li/SOCl₂) primary batteries possess the highest energy density and longest storage life of currently flown battery chemistries.

Active small cell modular lithium battery [8] -- A battery consisting of modules of 10 Li-BCX DD-cells in series would assume a low development risk. The electrolyte is thionyl chloride with a BrCl complexing agent. The D-cell version in the BCX chemistry is flight qualified with extensive experience. Qualification of the DD-cell would be a simple extrapolation of the D-cell effort performed at JSC by the Propulsion and Power Division. The DD-cell is twice as long as a D-cell but with the same diameter. The DD-cell to be qualified would offer a 3.0 A rate at 3.0 V for 25 Ah in a 0.5 lb package. A ten-cells-in-series module would provide 750 Wh of energy at 30 V for a 6 lb and 120 in³ package. This package would include parallel by-pass diodes on each cell, a blocking diode, and several thermostats to prevent surpassing the maximum operating temperature of 160 °F. The modular approach permits accommodation of failure tolerance with minimal mass/volume impact by including extra modules. A five year shelf life can be confidently extrapolated from 2 year test data obtained at JSC. However, some passive thermal control would be required in the design to maintain the cells as close as possible to a constant 0 °F to maximize storage life.

Active large cell modular lithium battery -- A battery consisting of large (250 Ah) Li/SOCl₂ modules connected in parallel could meet the CERV requirements. One is currently under development for the Centaur Upper Stage. It consists of nine cells in series for a design weight of 75 lb and 1070 in³ (100 Wh/lb and 7.0 Wh/in³). The advantages of this system is less modules, high volumetric energy density, high projected storage life (7 years at 0 °F), and a near term (qualified by 1990) development funded by the Air Force. The disadvantages are that it is optimized for higher rates (5 hours) which results in lower gravimetric energy density, and the design is not man-rated.

Reserve large cell modular lithium battery -- A reserve battery stores its electrolyte in a separate reservoir from the cell electrodes to provide long term inactive storage with minimal capacity loss and minimal sensitivity to temperature fluctuations. It also provides an inherent in-

creased safety during inactive storage since the internal short hazard is only present after activation. The activation of a reserve battery can be done by pyrotechnically generating a gas which pressures piston to push the electrolyte into the dry cells. The proposed configuration is a large 250 Ah nine-cells-in-series Li/SOCl₂ module providing 7500 Wh at 75 lb and 1.0 ft³ (100 Wh/lb, 4.2 Wh/in³). Failure tolerance is met by including extra modules. Several military programs have advanced the technology for missile, torpedo, and sonobuoy decoy applications and are presently close to or during qualification [9]. However, these are smaller (25 Ah or less) cells designed for high power density. A higher development risk would be assumed for the scale-up to a 250 Ah cell relative to the active configurations. Generally, a reserve system weighs 20% more and consumes 80% more volume than an equivalent active system. However, this impact to the CERV vehicle could be nearly eliminated by jettisoning the electrolyte storage reservoir after activation. Activation from a cold start takes less than a minute. The reserve concept eliminates the need for cooling and the energy/power margins included in the active systems for degradation during inactive storage.

Fuel cell with gaseous H₂, O₂ -- A solid polymer electrolyte fuel cell using a Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) can meet the power levels with a stack of 34 cells weighing 50 lb. This is similar to the technology used for Gemini capsules and is proposed for the ESA Hermes Shuttle. The main advantage of this system over alkaline fuel cells which are used on the Shuttle, is the lack of free liquid electrolyte which increases reliability. Combined with gaseous reactant storage at 3000 psi, the energy density of this system is good gravimetrically (148 Wh/lb). However, fuel cells have inherent disadvantages when compared to batteries for this application in terms of maintainability, complexity, cold starting capability, and low volumetric energy density due to gaseous storage. Also, this sizing estimate given in Table IV does not reflect a system which meets the failure tolerance requirements. Meeting this requirement could result in a substantial increase weight and volume impact.

Table IV. SPE PEM Fuel Cell System (100 kWh)

Component	Mass (lb)	Vol (ft ³)
Fuel cell stack	50	1.0
Oxygen	109	
Hydrogen	13	
O ₂ tanks (5 total)	170	5.5
H ₂ tanks (5 total)	385	11.0
Total	677	17.5

Photovoltaic/battery hybrid -- This system consists of a primary lithium battery for the three planned mission phases and rechargeable Ni-H₂ batteries coupled with Ga-As solar arrays for the contingency on-orbit loiter phase. The intent of this coupled system is to allow unlimited on-orbit time capability and maximum flexibility by conserving primary power for the on-orbit, entry, and recovery phases. This system provides regenerative power if more than 2 hours are needed for the initial on-orbit phase. The solar arrays could be deployed and then restowed or jettisoned before entry. Specifically, a large array power (6504 W) requiring 288 ft² is needed to provide 2710 W for the power down contingency phase and to recharge the batteries during the light cycle [10]. The secondary system including arrays, batteries, charger, regulator and accessories is 401 lb and 16.4 ft³ [11]. The primary power for the planned phases requires a high rate source like the JPL Li/SOCl₂ D-cell. A battery consisting of 50 ten-cells-in-series modules would meet the 12,775 Wh of energy required with several extra modules for failure tolerance. This D-cell is currently in its final stages of development and would require a qualification effort equal to the Li-BCX D-cell work done at JSC. The primary system would add 150 lb and 1.8 ft³ to the total hybrid power system. Half of the total 18.2 ft³ designated for the hybrid system is allocated to the solar arrays. This volume impact to the CERV could be reduced by containing the array externally and jettisoning them before entry. However, additional weight and volume margins to meet the failure tolerance have not been included in the estimates (Table V) and could be substantial due to the complexity of the system.

Table V. Photovoltaic/Battery Hybrid System

Component	Mass (lb)	Vol (ft ³)
Primary power system		
JPL Li/SOCl ₂ D-cell modular battery		
Each module = 10 cells in series		
30V, 3A, 300 Wh, 3 lb, 60 in ³		
50 parallel modules (15 kWh)	150	1.8
Secondary power system		
Ga-As solar arrays sizing factor = 2.4 *		
Solar array power = (factor)(dark cycle power)		
6504W = 2.4 x 2710 W		
Power density = 26.4 lb/kW 172		
22.6 W/ft ² , array area = 288 ft ²		
Thickness = 0.4 in, total array		9.5
Ni-H ₂ batteries provide 2710W		
Energy=(2710W)(0.6h)=1626Wh		
Energy density = 16 Wh/lb	102	
Energy density = 566 Wh/ft ³		2.9
Accessories (charger, rad.)**	35	1.0
Subtotal	459	15.2
Structure, integration, & growth	92	3.0
Total system	551	18.2
*ref [10]		
**ref [11]		

Other options -- Other sources such as secondary batteries (Pb-acid, Ni-Cd, Ni-H₂, and Ag-Zn) offer low development risks but are too heavy and bulky. Lithium/polycarbon monofluoride (Li/CF_x) batteries offer high energy density, yet can not meet the high rate demand of DRM-1. Thermal batteries offer long storage life, but are also very heavy.

Baseline Selection

The five systems examined in detail are compared in Table VI. The Hybrid system offers the most performance (unlimited loiter time) at the lowest weight, but at the expense of volume and complexity. Primary Li/SOCl₂ batteries are the simplest, most reliable, least capacious, and most cost effective of the power systems compared. The active Li-BCX and Centaur battery systems offer low development risk at the cost of a temperature dependent storage life and a continuous exposure to possible short circuit induced critical failures.

Table VI. Mass/Volume Comparison

System	Mass (lb)	Vol (ft ³)
Active small cell Li/SOCl ₂	900	10.5
Active large cell Li/SOCl ₂	1125	8.3
Reserve large cell Li/SOCl ₂	1125	15.0
Fuel Cell with gaseous O ₂ ,H ₂	677	17.5
Photovoltaic/battery hybrid	551	18.2

The reserve Li/SOCl₂ configuration offers unlimited, temperature independent storage life at a higher development risk and higher volume. Also, load voltage checks are not possible with an inactivated reserve battery. However, electrolyte pressure in the reservoir and ohmic resistance across the dry cell can serve as checks for presence of electrolyte leakage and internal cell shorts, respectively.

The active Li-BCX DD-cell modular battery system is selected as the baseline electrical power source for the CERV due to the maturity of its man-rated design, and low development costs. However, the development of a reserve system is also under way due to its promise for long life which will reduce recurring costs over the life of each CERV, since power has been identified as the life-limiting subsystem of the CERV.

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Fig. 1. The Apollo derived CERV design by JSC.

Procedure:
 Intravehicular activity crew entry
 Disconnect umbilicals and stow
 Secure hatches
 Depressurize adapter volume
 Check out CRV
 Initiate pyrotechnic separation
 Maneuver with service module

Fig. 2. Space Station - CERV separation upon activation.

Fig. 3. Separation of CERV crew module from propulsion module after de-orbit burn.

Fig. 4. Parachute deployment typical of Apollo spacecraft water landing.